

Biogenetic-Type Transformation of Germacranolide to Melampolides

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A direct, single-step, biogenetic-type oxidative transformation of costunolide (I), the structural prototype of the germacranolides with $\Delta^{4(6)}$ *trans*- $\Delta^{1(10)}$ *trans*-double bonds, using selenium dioxide, led to the formation of two melampolides, (XIII) and (XIV), with $\Delta^{4(6)}$ *trans*- $\Delta^{1(10)}$ *cis* configurations. In addition to the chemical evidence, spectral data including NOE, are adduced to establish the stereostructures of the products.

SINCE the first isolation¹ of costunolide (I), the structural prototype of the germacranolides from costus root oil (*Saussurea lappa* Clarke, fam: Compositae), a broad spectrum of closely related sesquiterpene lactones, such as, albicolide(II)², urospermal (III)³, etc., have been reported. The typical feature of these compounds is that majority of them have undergone biogenetically mediated oxidative modifications at various centres in their carbocyclic ring skeleton. However, not much has been reported regarding the possible biogenetic-type oxidative transformations of these compounds. We report a simple, single-step transformation of costunolide (I) under mild conditions to two novel melampolides—an aldehydolactone (XIII) and the corresponding hydroxylactone (XIV). These lactones are structurally related to the melampolides, melampodin (IV)⁴ and frutescin (V)⁵.

Costunolide (I), on treatment with selenium dioxide (1:1.4 moles) in aqueous ethanol at $45 \pm 2^\circ$, in nitrogen atmosphere for a period of five hours, afforded a mixture of (XIII) and (XIV).

Since (XIII) and (XIV) retained the α -methylene- γ lactone moiety, their isolation was conveniently effected by the chromatographic separation of their crystalline morpholine adducts (XI) and (XII) and subsequent regeneration of the parent lactones under mild conditions via treatment of the quaternary methiodide with sodium bicarbonate⁷.

The adduct (XI) in its PMR spectrum (60 MHz) revealed a typical singlet at 9.6 $\dagger$ (1H) due to CHO. The appearance of the only singlet at 1.9 (3H) attributable to the C₄-methyl led to the conclusion that the C₁₀-methyl has undergone selective allylic

oxidation. The adduct (XI) on reduction using sodium borohydride in methanol yielded (XII).

The regenerated aldehydolactone (XIII) in its PMR spectrum (60 MHz) revealed the diagnostic narrow doublets at 6.2 (1H, $J=3$ Hz) and at 5.5 (1H, $J=3.0$ Hz) ($>=CH_2$). The singlets at 9.55 (1H) and at 1.9 (3H) were assigned to the CHO and the C₄-methyl respectively. It also afforded a crystalline semicarbazone.

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‡ PMR signals are in δ (ppm) units

The hydroxy lactone (XIV) showed PMR signal at 2.48 assigned to the OH (disappeared on D₂O exchange). On hydrogenation over Pd/C, (XIV) yielded a dihydroderivative XV.

Similar experiments utilising dihydrocostunolide (XVIII), yielded a mixture of the corresponding dihydroaldehydolactone (XIX) and the dihydrohydroxylactone, which were separated *via* the semicarbazone of the former. The dihydrohydroxy lactone, thus obtained, was identical with (XV).

Comparison of the UV absorption maxima of the lactones (XIII) and (XIV) [λ_{max} . 212, 226; 212 nm respectively] with that of (II), (III), (IV) and (V) [λ_{max} . 212; strong end absorption and 212; 214; 211 nm respectively] also indicated^{1,2} that the double bonds in (XIII) and (XIV) are located as $\Delta^{1,(1'0)}$ and $\Delta^{4,(5)}$. If the $\Delta^{1,(1'0)}$ double bond in (XIII) and (XIV) had migrated to $\Delta^{9,(1'0)}$, then their λ_{max} values would have been comparable with that of (VIII), (IX) and (X) [λ_{max} . 204; 202; 203 respectively]^{1,2}.

In conformity with the spectral conclusions, ozonolysis of (XIII), followed by oxidation with hydrogen peroxide, yielded levulenic acid (2,4-DNP, m.p. 206°)^{9a} as one of the products and not its next higher homologue, 2-oxohexanoic acid (2,4-DNP, m.p. 143°)^{9b}, thereby confirming that the double bond was in $\Delta^{1,(1'0)}$ position and had not migrated to $\Delta^{9,(1'0)}$ position during this transformation^{1,0}.

To further confirm the location of this double bond, and particularly to decide its stereochemistry, additional experiments were carried out. Because of the superposition of the signals in the 60 MHz spectrum of (XIII), due to protons at C₁, C₉ etc., in the regions relevant to a decisive solution of this stereochemical

problem, the PMR spectra of a degassed sample of (XIII) in two different solvents, CDCl₃ and DMSO-d₆, were run in 90 MHz with subsequent double irradiation of the signals due to various protons. The Nuclear Overhauser Effect (NOE) experiments further led to the unambiguous configuration of the $\Delta^{1,(1'0)}$ double bond as $\Delta^{1,(1'0)}$ *cis*, the $\Delta^{4,(5)}$ double bond having retained its original *trans*-configuration.

The comparative value of the PMR signals [partial structure (A) and also structure (XIV)] of the protons H_{3 β} , H₅, H₆, H₇, H_{13a} and H_{13b} in CDCl₃ and DMSO-d₆, which led to the establishment of the partial structure (A) for (XIII) are shown in Table-1. The relevant arguments are as follows.

TABLE-1.

(A)

	δ_{CDCl_3}	δ_{DMSO}		
H ₅	5.04	5.04	J _{3β,5}	= 0.5Hz
H ₆	4.57	4.77	J _{1β,6}	= 1
H _{13a}	5.47	5.46	J _{5,6}	= 10.3
H _{13b}	6.16	5.96	J _{6,7}	= 9.2
H ₉	2.2*		J _{7,13a}	= 32
H	2.2*		J _{7,H13b}	= 3.6

* Not observed but indicated by decoupling experiments

Irradiation at the frequency corresponding to $H_{1\beta}$ resulted in the collapse of the broadened doublet at 5.04 to a clean doublet by removal of $J_{\beta,1\beta}$. Also, the irradiation at the frequency of H_{β} , led $H_{1\beta}$ to appear as a sharp singlet. Further, while irradiating at the frequency of H_7 (*vide infra*), the H_{β} signal sharpened significantly indicating the presence of an allylic coupling of H_{β} to one of the H_{α} protons ($J_{\beta,\alpha} > 0.5$); the proton responsible for this was subsequently located to be $H_{\alpha\beta}$.

Irradiation at the frequency of H_{α} resulted in the partial collapse of H_{β} at 4.57. But the reverse experiment resulted only in partial collapse of H_{β} to a broadened singlet. However, in view of the power levels employed and the relatively small difference in chemical shift between H_{α} and H_{β} , the result is interpreted as significant. Additional evidence supporting this assignment is the apparent AB character of H_{α} and H_{β} .

Concomitant with the collapse of H_{α} , it was expected that the resonance between 2.7 and 3.4 would alter, since this signal was originally tentatively attributed to H_7 . Since this was not the case, H_7 was not located in this region. This conclusion was reinforced by the observation that irradiation at the frequencies of $H_{1\alpha a}$ and $H_{1\alpha b}$ did not produce a change in the signal centred at 3.0. Changes were observed in the region near 2.2 and irradiation at that frequency resulted in the collapse of both $H_{1\alpha a}$ and $H_{1\alpha b}$ to singlets and of H_{α} to a doublet.

This set of experiments did not give a unique solution to the problem of the structure fragment (A) of (XIII), but located H_7 unambiguously, and showed that H_{α} is coupled to a proton with the same or similar chemical shift.

The arguments which led to the partial structure (B) of (XIII) have been discussed below. The PMR signals of H_1 , $H_{\alpha\beta}$ and $H_{1\alpha}$ in $CDCl_3$ and $DMSO-d_6$ have been given in Table-2.

TABLE-2.

(B)

	δ_{CDCl_3}	δ_{DMSO}
H_1	6.53	6.61
$H_{\alpha\beta}$	2.96	2.76
$H_{1\alpha}$	9.46	9.39

The attempt to determine this fragment (B) of (XIII) began with the irradiation at the frequency of $H_{1\alpha}$ (narrowly split signal at 9.46) as a point of entry into the ring. This produced no change in the appearance of the signal assigned to the proton at the β -position of the conjugated system (later identified with H_1) which confirmed that the α , β -unsaturated carbonyl system was planar (no allylic coupling). However, the same experiment run under 'Nuclear Overhauser' conditions produced a 33.8% enhancement in the signal of the β -proton. Conversely, irradiation of H_1 produced a 26.3% enhancement in the signal strength of $H_{1\alpha}$. Hence, the double bond at $\Delta^{1,(10)}$ or $\Delta^{9,(10)}$ has been established as *cis*. The location of the double bond could not be established at that time. An additional piece of information gained by decoupling $H_{1\alpha}$ was that the splitting of $H_{1\alpha}$ (1.2 Hz) was not due to coupling with the proton responsible for the signal at 2.76 ($DMSO-d_6$) but rather due to coupling with a proton centred approximately at 2.08. This was confirmed by observing the $-CHO$ proton when the region between 1.97 and 2.18 was irradiated.

NOE Experiments

The NOE experimental data for various protons have been given in Table-3.

TABLE-3. % NOE-DATA

Irr / Obs	H_1	H_{α}	H_{β}	$H_{1\alpha}$	$H_{1\alpha a}$	$H_{1\alpha b}$
H_1	—	4.9	-1.0	33.8	10.8	$\Delta\delta = 0.37^b$
H_{α}	1.2	—	$\Delta\delta = 0.47^b$	6.3	$\Delta\delta = 0.43^b$	9.5 ^a
H_{β}	0.4	$\Delta\delta = 0.47^b$	—	12	0	5
$H_{1\alpha}$	2.1	$\Delta\delta = 0.47^b$	—	32	-4	-3
$H_{1\alpha a}$	26.3	-0.13	0.8	—	1.2	-0.8
$H_{1\alpha b}$	5.4	31.9	37.3	-1.8	17.9	-4.5

Details and interpretation of the superscripts of the Table—3 are as follows.

1. Irradiation of H_1 or H_5 produced significant NOEs' in signal of $H_{1,3}$, probably by intermolecular association (see structure XVI). Another possible explanation is the closeness between the saturating and the observation frequency.
2. Special experiment where spectrometer setting (field homogeneity, amplification) were not maintained constant, but the intensity of those protons which should not have varied were normalised to zero and the intensity of the other protons was adjusted accordingly.
3. New computer method, not yet tested adequately. Results probably not reliable.
4. Results need to be interpreted with caution since it was not possible to irradiate $H_{1,5}$ cleanly.
5. Difference between irradiating frequency and the frequency to be observed is too small to permit observation.

The most significant result was the detection of appreciable spin exchange between H_6 and $H_{1,4}$. Since the *cis*-nature of the conjugated double bond has been deduced previously the interaction between (and spatial proximity of) H_6 and $H_{1,4}$ requires a $\Delta^{1,(10)}$ double bond (model). The smaller interactions between H_5 and $H_{1,4}$ and between H_1 and H_6 are also in good agreement with a $\Delta^{1,(10)}$ structure.

It is clearly apparent from the models (structure XVI) that the only structure and configuration which will accommodate the observed NOEs' is that containing a $\Delta^{1,(10)}$ double bond, where the aldehyde group has an orientation best described as β -to the 'plane' of the ring while the C_4 -methyl group is α^{1B} .

Biogenetic considerations :

Biogenetically, this transformation provides a direct chemical evidence for the speculations that the germacranolides with $\Delta^{4,(5)}$ *trans*- $\Delta^{1,(10)}$ *trans* can undergo regio-specific isomerisation leading to melampolides with $\Delta^{4,(5)}$ *trans*- $\Delta^{1,(10)}$ *cis*-configuration. It is no longer possible tacitly to assume that a new germacranolide will be *trans-trans* at both $\Delta^{1,(10)}$ and $\Delta^{4,(5)}$ respectively.

Experimental

Rotations were taken in $CHCl_3$ unless otherwise stated. PMR spectra (60 MHz) were recorded on a Varian A-60 spectrometer and 90 MHz on a Bruker spectrometer with TMS as internal standard. Chemical shifts are expressed in δ and coupling constants in Hz. UV absorptions were in isopropanol recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, Model No. 137 and IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer Grating spectrophotometer, Model No. 257.

Isolation of (I)—It was isolated from the Kashmir and Punjab (India) costus root (*Saussurea lappa*, Clarke) oil by adopting the earlier documented procedure¹. Further purification, wherever necessary, was achieved via its morpholine-adduct, m.p. 105-6°, (α)_D+128° (c, 0.54); gave satisfactory elemental analysis. IR (nujol) 1757, 1656, 951 and 814 ($CH_2=C-CO-$) cm^{-1} ; PMR 6.16 and 5.5(1H d each; $J=3.5$; 13- H_2) 4.83 (2H, m H-10 and H-5); 4.7 (1H, d; $J=3.5$; H-6); 1.63 (3H, s; 4-Me); 1.41 (3H, s; 10-Me).

SeO₂ oxidation of (I)—To (I) (5 g) dissolved in aqueous ethanol (1:8, 175 ml), freshly sublimed SeO₂ (1.6 g) was added portionwise in 30 min. and the mixture agitated under N₂ for another 5 hr. at 45±2°. The precipitated selenium was filtered off, the solvent removed under vacuum at a bath temp. not exceeding 45° and the residue extracted with solvent ether (5×100 ml). The ethereal layer was washed with Na₂CO₃ (5%) solution, water and dried over anh. Na₂SO₄. Removal of ether yielded the product (A) (4.72 g) TLC-2 spots; no unreacted (I). IR (nujol) 3450, 1070 (OH); 1760, 1675, 815 ($CH_2=C-CO$) cm^{-1} .

(At elevated temperatures and with increased proportions of the oxidant, the reaction yielded essentially the same products, excepting that in the former case, the substrate undergoes rapid polymerisation leading to poor yields of the products.)

Preparation of the morpholine adducts (XI) and (XII)—To (A) (1 g) dissolved in ethanol (5 ml), morpholine (0.7 ml) was added at -10° with stirring and the mixture kept at the same temp. for 6-8 hr. Dilution with water and the usual work up furnished the mixture of adducts (B) (0.93 g) (TLC-2 spots). The mixture (0.925 g), obtained as above, was chromatographed over silica gel (Riedel) (15 g). Elution with solvent ether (3×50 ml) afforded (XI) (0.41 g), which was further purified by recrystallization from n-hexane-CHCl₃ (1:1), m.p. 112-3°; (α)_D-54.63° (c, 3.44); IR (nujol) 2815, 2720, 1770, 1665, 1625 (lactonic C=O and -CHO) cm^{-1} ; UV λ_{max} , 208 and 230 nm (ϵ 6014 and 6601); PMR (CDCl₃) 9.6 (1H, s, CHO); 6.5 (1H, m, H-1); 5.06 (1H, d, $J=10$ Hz; H-5); 4.6 (1H, d; $J=8$ Hz; H-6); 1.9 (3H, s; 4-Me) (Found C, 68.5; H, 7.97; N, 3.65. C₁₉H₂₇O₄N requires C, 68.44; H, 8.16; N, 4.20%).

Subsequent elution with methanol yielded (XII) (0.54 g) which was recrystallised from n-hexane:chloroform (1:1), m.p. 158-59°; (α)_D-5.33° (c, 3.006); IR (nujol) 3400, 1060 (OH), 1760 (lactonic C=O) cm^{-1} . (Found C, 68.17; H, 8.59; N, 4.26; C₁₉H₂₉O₄N requires C, 68.03; H, 8.71; N, 4.18%). Regeneration of (XIII) from (XI): (XI) (0.68 g) was treated with dry CH₃I (3 ml) for 30 min. with stirring and subsequently with aqueous Na₂CO₃ solution (5%)

for 24 hr. at 5°. Further work up yielded (XIII) (0.35 g) which on recrystallisation from n-hexane-CHCl₃ (1:1), showed m.p. 122-23° [α]_D -28.24° (c, 2.62); IR (nujol) 1765, 1675, 1410, 930 and 790 (CH₂=C-C=O)

cm⁻¹; UV λ_{max} . 212 and 226 nm (ϵ 6006 and 6431). PMR (60 MHz) (CDCl₃) 9.55 (1H, s, CHO); 6.2 (1H, d, $J=3$ Hz; H-13); 5.5 (1H, d; $J=3$ Hz; H-13); 6.5 (1H, m; H-1); 5.1 (1H, d; $J=10$ Hz; H-5); 5.46 (1H, t; $J=10$ Hz; H-6); 1.9 (3H, s; Me-4) (Found C, 72.12; H, 7.17; C₁₅H₁₈O₃ requires C, 73.14; H, 7.37%). Regeneration of (XIV) from (XII). (XII) (0.79 g) was treated with dry CH₃I (3 ml) and aqueous Na₂CO₃ solution (5%) according to the procedure described earlier, to yield (XIV) (0.48 g) which was recrystallised from n-hexane-CHCl₃ (1:1), m.p. 95-6° (collapses), [α]_D -102.08° (c, 3.06). IR (nujol) 3480 (OH); 1760, 1660, 1400, 955, 810 (CH₂=C-CO-) cm⁻¹; UV λ_{max} . 211 nm (ϵ 8394). (Found C, 72.65; H, 8.25; C₁₅H₂₀O₃ requires C, 72.55; H, 8.12%).

Isolation of (XIII) and (XIV) from product (A) via the semicarbazone of (XIII). To product (A) dissolved in ethanol (7 ml) was added a solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (0.8 g) and NaOAc (1.5 g) in aqueous ethanol (4 ml) at room temperature and the product set aside for 14 hr. Further work up yielded a mixture (0.970 g) of (XIV) and the semicarbazone of (XIII). This on chromatography over silica gel (Riedel) afforded (XIV) (0.37 g) and subsequent elution with methanol gave (XIII) as semicarbazone (0.45 g). The latter was recrystallised from n-hexane-CHCl₃ (1:1), m.p. 239-40°; IR (nujol) 1760, 1400, 945 and 805 (CH₂=C-CO-) cm⁻¹; UV λ_{max} . 212 and 268 nm (ϵ 18,050 and 12,890) (Found C, 63.20; H, 6.84; N, 13.67; C₁₆H₂₁O₃N₃ requires C, 63.35; H, 6.98; N, 13.65%).

Conversion of (XI) to (XII). To a well cooled solution of (XI) (0.10 g) in methanol (3 ml), NaBH₄ (25 mg) was added and stirred for 15 min. The product was kept at 5° for another 18 h. Further work up in the usual manner gave (XII) (80 mg), m.p. and mixed 158-59°.

Hydrogenation of (XIV) - (XIV). (950 mg) in ethanol (5 ml) was hydrogenated over Pd/C (5%, 20 mg) until one mole equivalent (4.5 ml) of hydrogen was absorbed. Further work up yielded (XV) (30 mg) which was recrystallised from n-hexane-CHCl₃ (1:1) m.p. 154-55°; IR (nujol) 3430 (OH), 1760 (lactonic C=O) cm⁻¹. (Found C, 72.12; H, 8.67; C₁₅H₂₂O₈ requires C, 71.97; H, 8.86%).

Ozonolysis of (XIII). A stream of ozonised oxygen was passed through a solution of (XIII) (75 mg) in methylene chloride (20 ml) at -10° till a solution of KI was turned orange. The ozonide was decomposed with water (5 ml) by refluxing the reaction mixture on a

water bath for 1 hr. It was then cooled and H₂O₂ (25.8%; 2.5 ml) was added and the mixture kept at the room temp overnight, diluted with water (3 ml) and extracted with ether (15 ml $\times$ 6). The ethereal layer was washed with water and dried over Na₂SO₄ (anh). Removal of ether yielded a product which gave positive CHI₃ test. This was mixed with aqueous NaHCO₃ solution (10 ml), thoroughly shaken and then extracted with ether (15 ml $\times$ 6). The aqueous and the ethereal layers were separated. The aqueous layer was acidified with HCl (diluted, 5 ml) and extracted with CHCl₃ (10 ml $\times$ 8). The CHCl₃ layer was then washed with a little water and dried over Na₂SO₄.

Removal of CHCl₃ yielded a mixture of acids (25 mg) which was redissolved in MeOH (1 ml) and mixed with DNP reagent in methanolic sulphuric acid (0.8 ml). The DNP-derivative thus obtained was subjected to preparative thin layer chromatography over silica gel (12g/plate) and the laevulenic acid DNP was separated (12 mg) and characterised by comparison with authentic sample (mp, mixed mp, TLC and IR).

Hydrogenation of (I) to dihydrocostunolide (XVIII). This was carried out according to the procedure reported¹. The product obtained exhibited m.p. 76-77°, [α]_D +112.5° (c, 2.8); showed satisfactory elemental analysis and spectral characteristics.

SeO₂ oxidation of dihydrocostunolide. To dihydrocostunolide (3 g) dissolved in aqueous ethanol (1:8, 75 ml), was added freshly sublimed SeO₂ (1 g) during 30 min and the mixture stirred in a current of N₂ for 5 hr. at 45 $\pm$ 2°. Further work up yielded the product (C) (2.30 g).

To the product (C) (1 g) dissolved in ethanol (7 ml) was added an aqueous ethanolic solution of (2:3, 12 ml) semicarbazide hydrochloride (1.2 g) and sodium acetate (1.5 g) and the mixture was left for 18 hr. at the room temp. Further work up yielded the dihydroaldehydolactone semicarbazone and (XV) as a mixture (0.970 g) (D).

Isolation of (XV) from (D) - (D) was chromatographed over silica gel (Riedel, 7 g). Elution with solvent ether yielded (XV) (320 mg).

Isolation of dihydroaldehydolactone semicarbazone from (D) - After the selective elution of (XV), subsequent elution with methanol afforded the dihydroaldehydolactone semicarbazone (610 mg) m.p. 180-2°. (Found C, 62.67; H, 7.38; N, 3.98. C₁₈H₂₂O₃N₃ requires C, 62.93; H, 7.59; N, 13.76%).

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